

Delayed Presentation of Rhisoimmunization: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

This research article presents a case study of a 2-month-old male neonate with Rh isoimmunization and its associated complications. The patient exhibited symptoms such as blackish colour spots over the body, petechial rashes over the abdomen, and vomiting. The article discusses the patient's medical history, examination findings, and relevant investigations. The treatment course, including blood transfusion, IVIG administration, and medication, is described. The article emphasizes the delayed presentation of Rh isoimmunization from neonatal age to infancy with importance of close monitoring, follow-up care, and further investigations to intervene at timely basis provide best healthcare for the recovery of the patient. This case highlights the challenges associated with Rh isoimmunization in neonates and the need for prompt diagnosis and management.

Keywords: Blackish colour spots; Rashes; Vomiting

INTRODUCTION

Rh isoimmunization is a condition that occurs when a mother with Rh-negative blood type produces antibodies against Rh-positive fetal red blood cells during pregnancy. This immune response can result in severe complications for the newborn, including hemolytic disease and delayed hemolytic reactions- causing anemia and jaundice of varying intensity in the early postnatal period and is usually treated with phototherapy but some may be refractory and require IVIG and exchange transfusion. This case study focuses on delayed presentation of RH isoimmunization of a 2-month-old male neonate who presented with severe anemia with hepatosplenomegaly with cutaneous manifestations (petechiae and multiple blackish spots over face and abdomen)

CASE PRESENTATION

The article provides a detailed overview of case about two-month old infant, with above mentioned complaints, work up, hospital course and early intervention of the case and good outcome and normal growth status on follow up visits.

2 months old infant born out of non-consanguineous marriage with blackish colour spots and petechial rashes over body (face and abdomen) for 3 days. On eliciting further history, baby was born at 36 weeks' gestation, received 2 intrauterine transfusions in view of immune hydrops fetalis. During the postnatal stay in NICU, baby had pathological Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia for that he received Double surface phototherapy.

Examination Findings

On examination child was pale, petechial rashes and multiple blackish spots over face and abdomen were seen, pulse rate and respiratory rate were 136 beats/min, 33 breaths/ min respectively. On systemic examination he had hepatosplenomegaly (liver palpable 4 cm below right costal margin and spleen palpable 3 cm below left costal margin). On further evaluation investigations showed anemia(Hemoglobin: 3.79 gm/dl),leukocytosis (Total cell count: 17990 /cumm), thrombocytopenia (platelets: 84000 cells/cumm), peripheral smear showed moderate anisocytosis with presence of normocytic normochromic red blood cells with few macrocytes with normal white blood cell counts and distribution for age with reduced Platelets count, reticulocyte count was 1.5%. Biochemical evaluation showed total serum bilirubin 3.2mg/dl, unconjugated bilirubin: 2.29mg/dl, lactate dehydrogenase was raised (LDH: 1829), and positive- direct antiglobulin test (DAT) and indirect antiglobulin test (IAT). Ultrasound abdomen showed hepatosplenomegaly with normal liver echotexture and no other significant abnormalities noted.

Treatment and Management

After examination, relevant investigations were sent. As it was k/c/o Rh isoimmunization, work up for hemolysis was positive. Daily Complete blood count was done to monitor the fall in Hemoglobin and look for thrombocytopenia, where necessary blood products were transfused accordingly during the hospital stay. Ruling out other possibilities was the primary concern in this case, Congenital infections (TORCH panel- Toxoplasmosis, others like Parvovirus B19, Syphilis, Varicella zoster virus, Listeria monocytogenes, Rubella, Cytomegalo virus, Herpes simplex virus-2) and index case being male infant, possibility of Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase was also ruled out. Gradually there was no improvement initially fall in Hb and platelets were seen, later infant was given intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) (1gram/kg) over 2 days. Hematinic (oral iron, Folic acid), vitamin B12 supplements with adequate nutritional support were given. During fourth day of the hospital stay there was improvement in the hemogram with rise in hemoglobin and platelet count (complete blood count which revealed Hemoglobin: 7.2 gm/dl, Total cell count: 6900, platelets:104000/cumm) and irritability of the infant and clinical

status started improving and oral feeds were established completely by day six of stay and was discharged in hemodynamically stable state with follow up advice.

Follow-up and Monitoring

Infants was advised for follow up on regular basis. The parents were counselled on the nature of their child's illness, the implications of anti-D prophylaxis, and a high risk of complications during subsequent pregnancies if not taken. Contraception was advised. Follow-up visits after one week and monthly for next two months showed that the child was thriving well in growth and developmentally normal (**Figure 1**) and his haemoglobin concentrations were within the reference range.

Figure 1: One-Year old

DISCUSSION

Rh isoimmunization is a preventable disease in which an Rh-negative mother develops antibodies against paternal Rh antigen on foetal RBCs. These antibodies are generated by exposure of the fetal blood into the maternal circulation, resulting from fetomaternal haemorrhage secondary to a previous pregnancy, abortion, trauma, or invasive procedure. This phenomenon known as allo-immunization is safe in first Rh negative pregnancy but would be dangerous on subsequent pregnancies. Sensitization usually does not affect the firstborn child but can cause haemolytic disease in subsequent newborns. Isoimmunization of Rh-negative pregnant women can be prevented by administering a prophylactic dose of anti-D immunoglobulin, which neutralizes the effect of these isoantibodies. A failure or delay in this, would cause destruction of fetal RBC's causing haemolytic disease of Newborn and requires exchange transfusion and phototherapy. Although Rh isoimmunization was the main cause of neonatal and perinatal

morbidity and mortality for many years, this rate was markedly reduced following the introduction of anti-D immunoglobulin prophylaxis ^[1,2]

Rh isoimmunization is responsible for neonatal anemia, which varies in severity from fetal hydrops in utero to mild-to-severe anemia during the immediate postnatal period ^[3]. These isoantibodies may continue to destroy fetal RBCs for four to six weeks postnatally ^[4]. Continued destruction may be due to lack of recognition of symptoms and appropriate treatment or a progressive improvement in reticuloendothelial function during the second week of life ^[5]. Because of the parallel maturation of the liver, this increased rate of haemolysis may not always be associated with an increase in serum bilirubin concentration

CONCLUSION

The case described here demonstrates that all infants with HDN due to Rh isoimmunization should be considered at risk for late anaemia, even in the absence of jaundice or anaemia during the immediate postnatal period. Rapid diagnosis for early intervention and periodic examinations after discharge, including repeat measurements of haemoglobin concentrations, are necessary. Parents should be counselled about the importance of timely medical attention to symptoms of anaemia and the necessity of prophylactic anti-D immunoglobulin.

Ethical Considerations

The article ensures that patient confidentiality and ethical considerations were maintained throughout the study and that appropriate informed consent was obtained. This research article provides valuable insights into the clinical presentation, diagnosis, and management of Rh isoimmunization, highlighting the importance of multidisciplinary care and long-term follow-up.

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